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Flight Safety and the Key Role of Flight Attendants

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Abstract

A cabin crew member reports on the key role of flight attendants in flight safety management.

Keywords

cabin, safety, cabin crew, fume event, contaminant

The Cabin Safety section of the International Civil Aviation Organization website says, “Cabin safety contributes to the prevention of accidents and incidents; the protection of the aircraft’s occupants, through proactive safety management, including hazard identification and safety risk management; and the increase of survival in the event of an emergency situation.” (ICAO 2021).

Cabin crew members are qualified staff who play an important proactive role in managing safety before passengers boarding, during the flight and after disembarking, cabin crew are primarily focused on the prevention of accidents. The safety role of the cabin crew is voluntarily not always blatant because a key part of our job involves the so called “Emotional labor”, in few words we need to be able to manage our feelings and our expressions when we work, especially during interactions with customers and co-workers. This is part of our training on crowd management for example. When we welcome our customers, we are trained to immediately start to evaluate their behavior especially of those sitting in the emergency rows, because we always need to be prepared for a sudden safety occurrence which may need passengers help or preventing unlawful interference and managing passenger events that can compromise safety and security of the flight, such as hijackings. Cabin crew role is not only key to preventing incidents from escalating in the cabin but it includes also being able to adequately inform the flight crew of abnormal situations observed in the cabin or relating to the aircraft, such as pressurization problems or engine anomalies.

In 2019 during their annual conference presentation, ICAO recommended some key publications to stakeholders with the aim to highlight some possible safety threats and errors, risk scenarios and aircraft accidents also affecting the cabin crew’s safety area of competence, one of this is the Circular 344 titled Guidelines on Education, Training and Reporting Practices related to Fume Events, published back in 2015 (ICAO 2015). The flight safety implications of crew members' exposure to oil fumes sourced to the aircraft air supply system, are proven to be highly dangerous that’s why the ICAO has developed guidance material to improve awareness and training of all crew, related to the management of fume events. At any airline level in fact any deficiencies and/or unserviceability of safety equipment or

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systems must always be reported to enable appropriate mandatory reporting to be made. It is in the interests of safety to ensure the full, free and uninhibited reporting of all incidents that affect flight safety.

When it comes to report a fume event, especially when there is no strong smell or no clear smoke in the cabin it is always very difficult to file a report. In some airlines cabin crew cannot directly report fume events, even if they might be systemic failing which could easily result in a repeated event. These kind of events that should be addressed with priority have sometimes to follow a very complicated procedure which implies that the cabin crew first speak to the commander who must then contact the head of pilots to seek verification that it is a “red flag” event and then only if this is confirmed the cabin crew can report the issue with such a priority. Most fume events that are contaminated air smell with no visible fumes then finish to be almost never reported - probably this happens 99% of the times. ICAO Guidelines on Education, Training and Reporting Practices related to Fume Events would recommend that all the crew is trained to recognize, characterize, respond to, and report fume events, without any obstacle, but not every airline has a specific training for cabin crew, nor suitable protective personal equipments.

In my long career now I have unfortunately encountered many crew whose health was affected as a result of exposure to these contaminants in the aviation environment. Some of them have developed chronic breathing difficulties and cognitive impairment, which include the inability to carry out routine tasks: skills you don't want any person to lose, especially any crew member.

There is extensive scientific literature on the toxicological consequences of repeated low dose exposure to chemicals. The health of cabin crew, pilots and passengers has to be put among the priorities, especially now where the Aviation has to be redesigned to face the post pandemic. On existing bleed air architecture aircraft, fugitive emissions from aircraft engines MUST be reduced to the minimum achievable using Best Available Technology (BAT). On future generations of aircraft all the airlines should be united to choose a bleed-free architecture

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About the Author

[Alessandra Airaldi](#) is a cabin crew member, specialized in the area of OH&S with her union and at a regional level, and one of the board members of the GCAQE, the global coalition of health and safety advocates committed to raising awareness and finding solutions to poor air quality on commercial aircraft.